

TO TAXONOMIC COMPOSITION OF ORIBATID MITES OF MARITIME ANTARCTICA

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Oribatida is a suborder of mites belonging to the order Sarcoptiformes within the superorder Acariformes of the subclass Acari. The known global diversity of oribatid mites includes more than 11,600 species representing 1,328 genera and 166 families. Of these, around 148 taxa are known from Antarctica (~100 species) and the sub-Antarctic islands (~54 species).

By "Maritime Antarctica" we mean the area that includes Bouvet Island, the South Sandwich Islands, the South Orkney Islands, and the South Shetland Islands, along with the western coast of the Antarctic Peninsula. According to literature data, a list of species of oribatid mites of the Maritime Antarctic region has been compiled. This taxa composition does not include those defined as "sp.". Thus, the taxonomic composition of oribatid mites in the Maritime Antarctica is as follows.

The family Brachychthoniidae includes species such as *Eobrachychthonius oudemansi* Hammen in 1952, along with *Liochthonius australis* (Covarrubias, 1968) and *Liochthonius mollis* (Hammer, 1958). These mites are typically small and known for their distinctive morphological features.

Within the family Oppiidae, several species have been included *Membranoppia loxolineata* (Wallwork, 1965) and *Austroppia crozetensis* (Richters, 1908). Additionally, *Brachioppiella pepitensis* (Hammer, 1962) is accompanied by a subspecies, *B. p.* subsp. *brevipectinata* (Covarrubias, 1968). Another species in this family is *Globoppia intermedia*, first described by Hammer in 1962.

The family Ameronothridae comprises a variety of taxons adapted to extreme environments. Among them, *Alaskozetes antarcticus* subsp. *antarcticus* (Michael, 1903), *A. a.* subsp. *intermedius* Wallwork in 1967 and *Alaskozetes bouvetoyaensis* (Pletzen and Kok, 1971). The genus *Halozetes* includes multiple taxons, such as *Halozetes belgicae* subsp. *belgicae* (Michael, 1903), *H. b.* subsp. *longisetae* (Wallwork, 1967), *H. impeditus* (Niedbala, 1986), *H. marinus* (Lohmann, 1907) and *H. necrophagus* (Wallwork, 1967).

The family Liebstaadiidae represented by only one species – *Totobates nordenskjoeldi* (Trägårdh, 1907).

The family Ceratozetidae includes several species, such as *Edwardzetes dentifer* (Hammer, 1962) and *Edwardzetes elongatus* (Wallwork, 1966). Additionally, *Magellozetes antarcticus* (Michael, 1895) and *Magellozetes processus* (Hammer, 1962) are among the representatives of this family. Another species is *Sphaerozetes polygonalis*, which was first described by Hammer in 1962.

Consequently, according to literature data, the taxonomic composition of Maritime Antarctic region of oribatid mites has been established, which is represented by 5 families, 12 genera, 19 species, and 5 subspecies.